

What is “Anthropotechnics”: on the Trail of a Transforming Concept

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Abstract: The paper explores the historical variations in the understanding of the notion of *anthropotechnics* by examining the reshaping of concepts embodied in the term, which is typically associated with scientifically based aspirations for human refinement and longevity.

Through this lens, the text comments on the biopolitical horizons of the 20th century, which permeate established political divisions through techniques of both (self-) governmentality and the discipline of the collective body.

Initially framed within the field of biology, the term denoted techniques similar to these in animal breeding, linking it with the concept of eugenics. During the 1960’s and 1970’s *anthropotechnics* entered the context of productivity intensification, engaging with the human-machine system. Its newest interpretations focus around concepts such as human enhancement and mind training.

The primary aim is to examine the extent to which this term signifies the transformations standing behind ideas such as “optimization”, “improvement” and “better life”. The analysis draws on a number of sources – literature, archival materials, and other relevant studies from the periods in question.

Keywords: anthropotechnics, eugenics, ergonomics, medicine, occupational safety

This text explores the historical transformations behind the understanding of the notion of *антропомехника/anthropotechnics* by investigating the reshaping of concepts embodied in the term. The latter usually denotes the *man-machine* interaction, and scientifically-based aspirations for longevity and regeneration of the human body, which also influenced such scientific endeavours as gerontology and immortology. I am interested not only in its definition(s) and implied meaning, but also in the fields that they are operating in – the domain of their implementation, its initial agents and the subjects towards which these techniques are directed.

My primary goal is to examine the extent to which this term signifies the transforming (biopolitically charged) ideas and techniques standing behind

concepts such as “improvement” and “better life” during the last two centuries. This exploration is closely tied to utopian and ideological movements across Europe. This will enable further examination of the biopolitical horizons which permeate the established political divisions via techniques for both (self) governmentality and disciplining of the collective body. Following Ralf Konersmann’s idea that such notions “do not only have a history, “they *are* their history””,¹ I intend to trace the trajectories of the concept of anthropotechnics, demonstrating how its meaning and application have been shaped *by* and *with* the historical contexts and intellectual currents in which it has been embedded. While the text refers to and comments on various interventions and ideas, its primary aim is to elaborate on the locus of anthropotechnics as a scientifically driven discipline or project with fluid boundaries. As such, it does not seek to explore the full spectrum of practices, prescriptions, and narratives that might be analytically interpreted as *anthropotechnical in scope* (i.e. techniques upon the human) via a philosophical or critical theory key.

Introduction. Conceptual Converging and Diverging

My interest in the topic was sparked by the first edition of the *Great Soviet Encyclopaedia* (1926), as it was briefly discussed by Tatjana Petzer’s paper “Ageless, Vital, Immortal. Human Transformation in 20th – Century Russian Science and Literature”. The encyclopaedic definition frames the term in two main lines. Firstly, as part of applied biology. Its aim is to improve ‘the physical and spiritual qualities of a person’ through the selection of parents with desirable traits and the endogamy of breeding partners (a process known as ‘breeding a breed within itself’), similar to techniques used in animal breeding [зоотехника]. This approach is closely tied to the concept of eugenics, which ultimately came to obscure it. It suggests the strive to transformation not only in terms of physical qualities, but of one’s very *psychological dispositions*. Secondly, it is defined as the “application of anthropometric data and psychotechnics” that were used especially for the purposes of professional selection. It serves similarly to another notion – that of *психотехника* [psychotechnics], but it focuses more on physical traits, rather than exclusively psychological ones.²

¹ LIGGIERI, K. Von der “Menschen-zucht” zur “Menschen-behandlung”. Zur Begriffsgeschichte der “Anthropotechnik”. – *Archiv für Begriffsgeschichte*, 2015, No. 57, p. 237.

² ШМИДТ, О. Большая советская энциклопедия. Советская энциклопедия. Том 3, 1926, pp. 131–132.

Therefore, an oscillation between scientifically (but also philosophically) based human “refinement”, and the measuring tools for it, could be noted. It must be pointed out the shift towards a specification of the term and its “addressees” as it is positioned in the field of labour, serving as a metric for assessing work capacity and suitability.³ The authors of the entry give four references, all from the first half of the 1920’s, two in Russian – Gurevich’s *Analysis of the Components of Motor Giftedness* (1925) and Krontovsky’s *Heredity and Constitution* (1925), and two in German – Baur’s *Lectures on General Constitution and Genetics* (1923) and Kretschmer’s *Physique and Character* (1925). These volumes examined questions like skills, mental abilities, and body-capacity both in genetic and hereditary terms, but also touched on the still popular theories that tried to determine one’s personality via their physical structure and likeness.⁴

The term did not remain ideologically neutral. Less than a decade after the publication of the first edition of the *Great Soviet Encyclopaedia*, in 1933, the authors of the book *Dialectical Materialism* described the cited and other scientific entries as important ideological articles that “provide an anti-Marxist interpretation of the subject and an anti-Marxist orientation for a wide range of readers”.⁵ The term was not included in the next editions of the *Great Soviet Encyclopaedia* (1949), as in the second half of the XX century eugenics gained increasingly more negative connotations. This notion was further reinforced in the Russian-Soviet post-war context, where eugenics was explicitly linked not only to bourgeois ideology but also to fascism. Nevertheless, the term continued to appear in various types of media, and research in this area was not completely eradicated but had to be presented under different forms, such as “medical genetics”.⁶

³ This explicit connotation is seen as specific for the Russian-Soviet context; see: LIGGIERI, K. Von der “Menschen-zucht”, pp. 235–258.

⁴ The work of the psychiatrist Ernst Kretschmer, for instance, suggested a typology of the body’s physical build. Each body type reflected given personality traits, based on genetic dispositions and environmental factors, that carried a predisposition towards different mental disorders. Cf.: HÄFNER, H. Ernst Kretschmer 1888–1964. – *Psychological Medicine*, August 1990, Vol. 20, Issue 3, pp. 487–492.

⁵ ДИАЛЕКТИЧЕСКИЙ МАТЕРИАЛИЗМ. Маркс, Энгельс, Ленин, Сталин. Москва: Партийное издательство, 1933, p. 442.

⁶ LIGGIERI, K. “[A]n der Front des Kampfes um den Menschen selbst”. *Anthropogenetik und Anthropotechnik im sowjetischen Diskurs der 1920er Jahre*. – *Berichte zur Wissenschaftsgeschichte*, 2016, No. 39, S. 178.

Visions of Longevity and the Russian-Soviet Anthropotechnics. A Preliminary Detour

Firstly, I will discuss Tatjana Petzer's interpretation as it presents facets of the penetration of anthropotechnical narratives into the social imagination. Petzer addresses the entanglement between scientific and fictional discourses concerning aging, bodily regeneration, longevity, and immortality, intertwining utopian narratives with the rapidly advancing fields of "experimental biological research and medical engineering"⁷ that is implied by the keyword *антропотехника/anthropotechnics*. That perception introduced into the debates a specific form of pathologization of the ageing processes and dying as diseases or imperfections of the living organism that had to be cured and/or repaired. The author examines three Russian-Soviet literary examples – from 1910, 1920, and 1970. They highlight the shifts and variations in scientific programs, the means and methods of implementation, and the scope of their operation – ranging "from the biological and individual to the environmental and collective."⁸

The first notable model is that of "physiological intervention" – it was not strictly focused on 'breeding', but included a series of different immunological techniques for the bettering of the physical and psychological state of humans (Mechnikov) in order to extend one's longevity. The most notorious examples, according Petzer, are the mutual blood transfusions and the appliance of biochemical serums, that were to affect not only the individual, but to transform society as a whole.⁹

The second illustration given by Petzer is Platonov's "electroimmunological vision". Its aim is combating mortality with the help of (micro)biological and technical achievements, while being informed by the proletarian discourse

⁷ PETZER, T. Ageless, Vital, Immortal. Human Transformation in 20th-Century Russian Science and Literature. – In: *Foreign Countries of Old Age*. Eds. D. GRAMSHAMMER-HOHL, O. HERGENRÖTHER. Verlag, Bielefeld, 2021, p. 253.

⁸ Op. cit., p. 253. As noted by Liggieri it is "difficult to draw a clear line between the utopian theoretical vision of a "new human being" and eugenic-practical breeding in Russian discourse, as there are many hybrid networks between science, art and politics that interact, stimulate each other and produce knowledge", see: LIGGIERI, K. Von der "Menschenzucht"... , S. 247.

⁹ An instance is Aleksandr Malinovskij – whiter and physician, known also under the alias Bogdanov, who in 1926 founded an Institute for Blood Transfusion in Moscow, where "the blood injected between young and old, sick and healthy, was used for rejuvenation in one case and for refinement in the other", see: PETZER, T. Ageless, Vital, Immortal..., p. 257.

and the Soviet ideal of the New Man. His proposed mechanization of the human body reflects the anthropotechnical strategies directed at “the new communist worker in the machine age, which was to be psycho-physically formed in the Central Institute for Labour”.¹⁰ This model focuses on the canalization and amplification of certain aspects of human existence via environmental influence (i.e. a more disciplinary approach), than to an immediate internal transformation. In Platonov’s work *anthropotechnics* seems to play the role a fictional, but comprehensive programme with its own philosophical background, scientific methods, and institutionalization. Its aim – to prolong one’s life and their capacity to work and create by dedication to chastity and via the means of electricity treatment. His characters meet the creator of the science of anthropotechnics while reading from their “manifesto”,¹¹ or when coming across the fictional Experimental Research Institute for Individual Anthropotechnics.

The later model of the “biocybernetic experiment”, on the other hand, is sparked by the rehabilitation of cybernetics across the Soviet Union, as the latter became one of “the ideologically determined human sciences”.¹² Similar to cybernetic systems, biology is understood here as a code that can be manipulated to counter various pathological states, as in the case of biocybernetics medicine and biocybernetics. The man-machine relation becomes rather symbiotic. The solution to human’s immortality shifts from the extension of one’s corporeal existence to a hybridization of man and technology, where the latter is supposed to host or accommodate his/her consciousness. Petzer illustrates this with another physician – Nikolaj Amosov, whose literary work “Notes from the Future” envisions a protagonist that faces such a cybernetic future society after elongated stay in *anabiosis*. While Amosov’s science fiction publication followed utopian vision, his scientific work on ageing and rejuvenation led on another popular gerontological trend at that time, namely – the development of exercise regimes.

¹⁰ Op. cit., p. 260.

¹¹ A passage of the work reads “For this – to inoculate man with chastity and progress, to unlock in him the talent for invention – I founded the science of anthropotechnics”.

“Founders of the new civilization, workers of communism, fighters against capitalism and against the elements of the universe, unite and (...) drink from the living spring of eternal strength and youth – chastity.”, see: ПЛАТОНОВ, А. Усомнившийся Макар. Собрание. Москва: Время, 2011, pp. 101–102.

¹² PETZER, T. Ageless, Vital, Immortal..., p. 263.

As we can see, certain notions focused on amplifying human abilities and overall vitality, as well as the specific methods for their achieving, were encapsulated under the term *антропотехника/anthropotechnics*. The latter were informed by and re-envisioned with regard to current scientific programs (in medicine, biology, physics, chemistry) and technical progress.¹³ We can assume that these reflected some of the explicit and implicit anatomo- and biopolitics, but also that of social engineering in the name of individual and collective refinement. They strived for longevity and durability beyond the health concern, as they implied forms of vitality that had also moral and axiological implications.

Finally – in the described cases such visions could be seen not only as science fiction, but also as pseudoscience or alternative doctrine. Some interpretations associate the term “антропотехника” with a range of diverse fields, including Calvinism, Scheler’s philosophical anthropology, practices aimed at mind expansion and self-improvement (as meditation, psychotherapy, etc.)¹⁴, as well as with the esoteric.¹⁵ At the same time, the notion seemingly shares common ground with current movements such as transhumanism – an aspect that will be briefly addressed in the next section.

Transforming Man – a Transforming Concept

As implied above, an extended investigation of the term’s trajectory shows that its primary scope exceeds that of postponing ageing. Although not a popular one, it continues to resurface in seemingly varying frameworks. For the purposes of this text, I will trace its transformations in relation to the cultural-historical and scientific contexts. The examination is based on sources (literature and archival materials) from the relevant periods in several languages and studies mainly from French and German researchers,¹⁶ starting from the most

¹³ According to some researchers in Russian-Soviet discourse “eugenic knowledge and research were merged with medicine” in a very early stage, cf.: LIGGIERI, K. Von der “Menschen-zucht”..., S. 247.

¹⁴ The convergence between eugenics and religion is also notable in Nikolai Koltsov’s (1872–1940) work. He was a biologist, co-founder and first president of the Russian Eugenics Society, who spoke of “eugenic religion”, that reflected the utopian notion of refined humanity, cf.: Op. cit., p. 249.

¹⁵ Cf.: ГРИЦАНОВ, А. Всемирная энциклопедия: Философия. АСТ, Мн.: Харвест, Современный литератор, 2001.

¹⁶ GOFFETTE, J. Anthropotechnie: cheminement d’un terme, concepts différents. – *Alliage*, 2010, no. 67 «Perfection et perfectionnement du corps», pp. 104–116; LIGGIERI, K.

popular current one, and then reviewing some of the earliest detectable publications onwards, in order to arrive back to the late 1970's.

Contemporary Philosophy, Medicine, and Anthropotechnics

One of the most widely known current iterations of the term originally appeared in German in 1999 with the philosophical works of Peter Sloterdijk.¹⁷ His interpretation sparked controversies, both because of the problematic uses of the term, linking it to eugenics, as well as in relation to the debates around the role of modern biotechnology in human life. At the core of his thesis lies the understanding that the human being is fundamentally incomplete, but substantially based in the world and their surroundings. Historically, we engage in process of (voluntary) self-taming via *technical instrumentalization of the objective world* as a way of compensation.¹⁸ This is precisely what is meant by “anthropotechnics” in this case, as it is closely related to the concept of *technè*, including modern biotechnologies.¹⁹

Other researchers, like Jerome Goffette, suggest the term as an alternative to the notion of *human enhancement*.²⁰ They maintain the idea that it denotes forms of modifying the human being and their body, but insist that the interventions falling under this category are not for medical or therapeutic purposes, even though medicine and enhancement may share common elements and language. Goffette's endeavours could be interpreted as a step towards the demedicalization of human enhancement (its scope, agents and methods), where *anthropotechnics*, could also refer to practices such as mind training and self-help, leaning to its use as a self-governmentality tool.

The notion, as we will see further, gravitates around the liaison between natural and artificial, human and machine (as a long-standing symbol of tech-

Von der “Menschen-zucht”..., S. 235–258; LIGGIERI, K. “[A]n der Front des Kampfes um den Menschen selbst”..., S. 165–184.

¹⁷ SLOTERDIJK, P. Rules for the Human Zoo: A Response to the Letter on Humanism. – Environment and Planning D: Society and Space, 2009, Volume 27, Issue 1, pp. 12–28.

¹⁸ See: МАНЧЕВ, Б. Тялото-Метаморфоза. София: Алтера, 2007, p. 26

¹⁹ Still, some researches, like Kevin Liggieri note that Sloterdijk's meaning and scope of the term shifts in the span of his own work, cf.: LIGGIERI, K. Von der “Menschen-zucht”..., S. 236.

²⁰ GOFFETTE, J. Enhancement: Why We Should Distinguish Anthropotechnics from Medicine. – In: Inquiring into Human Enhancement Interdisciplinary and International Perspectives. Eds.: S. BATEMAN, J. GAYON, S. ALLOUCHE, J. GOFFETTE, M. MARZANO. Macmillan UK, 2015, pp. 38–59.

nology), and (disciplinary) techniques, permeating fields like science and art.²¹ However, that liaison is not unidirectional and has at least several conceptual trajectories that treat the human being and their body as susceptible to different forms of taming and modelling.

Early Modern Anthropotechnics and Social Engineering

The early concept of anthropotechnics, concerned mainly with the practical implementation of optimization (in quantity and in quality) via forms of genetic taming, can be traced to at least the end of the XIX century. Although the term emerged within texts written in different languages, following the observations of Goffette and Liggieri, it could be stated in advance that the spread of the term in Germany and England was far less significant, in comparison to France and Russia, where the notion acquired more of a programme character.

In 1898 for example, the term features in a monthly journal for literature and science entitled *God's World* – an edition that bears the “for self-education” tagline. Here an article discussed the capitalization of the agricultural industry. The text’s main purpose was to present new technologies in the agricultural world and the successful production results emerging from animal breeding, plant selection, and environment control. Nevertheless, it concludes with the suggestion that the introduction of such techniques may be used for “improving the human race”. This was paralleled with the principles of zootechnics [зоотехника] and aimed to modify the physical, spiritual, and intellectual properties of the human being, thereby contributing to an overall “greater level of progress”. The aim is a positive selection that reflects the old expedient notion of “making man better” with modern means: “Is a human being worse than a horse or a greyhound? – the anthropologist asks – pedigrees of thoroughbred animals are carefully kept, so why shouldn’t man keep a pedigree of anthropological properties?”.²² According to the author, the task of anthropotechnics

²¹ For instance, the term “covers” also the man-machine/man-technology interplay in contemporary art and philosophy of aesthetics – an aspect that could not be examined in this text.

²² КРЖИВИЦКІЙ, Л. Капіталізація земледільчеської промисленности. – Мір'я Божій, Годъ VI-й. № 5-й, 1898, p. 178. It has to be noted that this passage, which can be found paraphrased in other of Krzywicki’s works, is in quotation, illustrating the thoughts of the “passionate followers” of the anthropotechnics, reefering most likely to Galton’s ideas. In this case, the original “родословня” could be translated as “pedigree” and as “genealogy”, both based on the concept of heredity and descend, but with a stress on the pure-bredness (and its keeping or purifying) in the former.

is “raising the level of the brain”²³ implying a strive for maximization of the mental properties (intelligence), over say, physical features. It is used mainly in the sphere of the prospective and within utopian frames, but it is still embedded in a practical empirical horizon – in this vision, the high increases in potato production as a result of soil cultivation, inspires the techniques for bettering the human race.²⁴

The author – the polish anthropologist Ludwik Krzywicki, later on had to defend his work against critiques, because of its similarity with eugenics, framing the notion of anthropotechnics as being “guided by a sense of moral responsibility of parents towards their descendants, [which] does not contradict “Marxism”.”²⁵ However, another encyclopedic entry on the topic, written also by Krzywicki, directly links it with this field.²⁶ The text starts again with the established conceptual transferase from zootechnics to anthropotechnics. Its approach is more historical as it describes key moments from the eugenics’ development – pivotal authors, works, and practical applications. Leading is Galton’s project, with extended attention to his interest in familial genealogies, which serve not only as a history of one’s kin, but also as a record on the physical and mental abilities of each of its members. Krzywicki mentions its reception in different countries – Germany and France – but focuses on the USA as the main example, where these ideas had gained normative legitimization by law in some states, particularly concerning marginalized groups of the population. The project combined disciplines such as medicine, hygiene, and anthropology, as well as methods of partners selection for the preservation and improvement of given traits/abilities with a number of reproductive restrictions. Here Krzywicki takes more of a critical stance, as the entry defines the ideas of anthropotechnics as “utopian” and “highly undemocratic in nature”. Nevertheless, as a tool for hereditary selection, it is regarded as theoretically accurate but too often applied to a “narrow class worldview”. Krzywicki’s po-

²³ Op. cit.

²⁴ While some commentators ascribe the “invention” of anthropotechnics to Russian eugenics, and to this author in particular, this is arbitrary. As demonstrated also by Liggieri, Krzywicki was most likely influenced directly by the French eugenic discourse, or was informed thought the works of the Polish sociologist Leon Winiarski, who based his theory of “social mechanics” on the concept of human breeding. Cf.: LIGGIERI, K. Von der “Menschen-zucht”..., S. 242–244.

²⁵ КРЖИВИЦКІЙ, Л. Письмо въ редакцію. – Русское богатство, 1903, № 7, р. 172.

²⁶ КРЖИВИЦКІЙ, Л. Антропотехника. – В: Новый энциклопедический словарь. Т. 3. Ред. К. К. АРСЕНЬЕВА. С.-Петербургъ: 1911, pp. 99–101.

sition is that a general knowledge and acceptance of the organic laws is needed in order to awake “a moral imperative not to allow a sick or incapacitated person to produce offspring”²⁷ in the name of “anthropological progress”. As a result, his justification gravitated around the necessity for internalization of such disposition as a common obligation and duty. Liggieri notes that for Krzywicki anthropotechnics could not be effective unless embraced through free choice, hence his strong opposition against other eugenic approaches interested in negative selection (via involuntary sterilization for example).²⁸

Other notable early figures engaged with the concept of applied eugenics and positive human breeding, as discussed by Liggieri, include Valerian Muravyov (1885–1930), who argued that the refinement of the human being could not be achieved through upbringing but through physical (genetic) transformation facilitated by modern science and technology; and Alexander Serebrovsky (1892–1948), who sought to improve and curate the population’s gene pool in order to create new types of humans, contributing to socialist progress. According to Liggieri, these views of anthropotechnics rest heavily on the expectations of future applicability (be it distant or near) and perceived the human body as a matter that lends itself to manipulation and modelling. Serebrovsky, for example, proposed a procreation plan, but thought that it would be acquired only after the abolishing of such “western values” like conjugal love. The success of such a type of organized positive selection therefore would be possible “under socialism – after the final destruction of the family, the transition to socialist education and the separation of love and procreation”.²⁹

* * *

Meanwhile, an earlier western establishment of the term is traceable back to the 1890’s in Léonce Manouvrier’s classification of sciences, where anthropotechnics is seen as part of anthropology, being one of the arts that *represent human actions*, including fields such as “medicine, hygiene, ethics, law, education and politics”.³⁰ The classification of this branch under the category of “arts” further suggests its design as an applied discipline, and it is cited in a number of English sources from the same period. This is confirmed also by

²⁷ Op. cit., p. 100.

²⁸ LIGGIERI, K. Von der “Menschen-zucht”..., S. 248

²⁹ Cited from: LIGGIERI, K. “[A]n der Front des Kampfes um den Menschen selbst”..., S. 177.

³⁰ MANOUVRIER. L. L’Anthropologie et le Droit. – *Revue internationale de sociologie*, April, 1894, no. 4, pp. 241–273.

Goffette, who estimates that in the French context the earliest period in the emergence of the notion of *anthropotechnie* is between 1880–1945.³¹ Kevin Liggieri, on the other hand, goes even deeper into the historical emergence of the concept, referring to Adolphe Félix Gatién-Arnoult’s *Doctrine Philosophique* (1834), where anthropotechnics is classified under the system of the social sciences.³² The notion found its definition once again in the 1890’s *Great Universal Dictionary of the 19th Century*, this time as “Zoology of the Human Species”.³³

Liggieri suggests that this paralleling orientation towards the ideas and means of zootechnics was informed very strongly by Charles Darwin’s theories. *On the Origin of Species* was translated in France by Clémence-Auguste Royer, who was a teacher and member of the Anthropological Society of Paris. Her interpretation of Darwin’s work was embedded in the socio-political context, going beyond the scientific scope of biology, analogising the “laws of nature” to the mechanics of society. This trend was continued further, for example, by Georges Comte Vacher de Lapouge who worked on the topic of social selection (via means of artificial insemination, genetic manipulation, etc.) and introduced the concept of eugenics in France.³⁴

This vision of anthropotechnics shares identical predicaments, but with a much more explicit focus on the notion of childcare, as in this context it came to provide a scientifically based modern version of the so-called *callipedia* that goes beyond the “popular advice on creating beautiful children to the science of creating children”.³⁵ According to Goffette, such concepts operated primarily at the population level, aiming to improve the species as a whole. They became the subject of public policies and involved categorizing individuals based on hierarchical criteria. This is also confirmed by Liggieri, who emphasizes that the child was its “experimental object”, thus introducing pedagogy into the interdisciplinary inventory of anthropotechnics. This particular approach was adopted also in Germany for instance, by the experimental psychologist Ernst

³¹ GOFFETTE, J. *Anthropotechnie: cheminement d’un terme, concepts différents...*, p. 107.

³² LIGGIERI, K. *Von der “Menschen-zucht”...*, S. 238.

³³ *Op. cit.*, S. 239.

³⁴ *Op. cit.*, S. 241.

³⁵ GOFFETTE, J. *Anthropotechnie: cheminement d’un terme, concepts différents...*, p. 107.

Meumann (1862–1915),³⁶ and similar traces can be found in some Russian sources. In 1922, for example, Pavel Blonsky wrote in his *Pedagogy* that anthropotechnics, already understood as “педотехника” [pedotechnics], should gain its disciplinary status homogeneously with zootechnics, etc.³⁷ – a concept also used by Aleksei Gastev – theorist of the scientific management of labour, which yet again points to the idea of practical applicability of these methods.

Goffette establishes a second period in France that unfurls between 1948 and 1980. It was marked by the downfall of the eugenic doctrine, and while its aims were deemed unacceptable, the relative unpopularity of the term *anthropotechnics* itself mitigated its next uses. In that context, the notion became broader, representing, on one hand, the “art of raising man” through scientifically informed pedagogy, and on the other, a means for the “maximum development of man”, once again combining scientific and social projects under this idea.

The 1948’s *Nouveau Larousse Universel* – a French language encyclopaedia – puts anthropotechnics again under the label “art”. Its purpose was to install in Man a certain “level” that reflects both his biological capacity and his “sociological development and education”.³⁸ A definition that says little concrete, but implies: 1) a juxtaposition between biological optimum and social upbringing, and 2) the need for specific techniques to ensure this process. Goffette’s investigation even suggests the existence of Anthropotechnics’ Institute, although its history is not fully known. The author of the work *Anthropotechnie – De la Science de l’Homme à l’Art de faire les Hommes* (1948) Jean Schunk de Golfiem was affiliated as its director. The book discusses physical anthropology’s theories from that period, presenting evolutionary processes as value-laden. It follows the eugenic ideas that scientific knowledge – in anatomy, medicine, hygiene, genetics, etc. – could, and should be applied for the “advance of humanity”, but focuses more on forms of positive sanction. Here anthropotechnics is defined as “[t]he sum total of all the techniques useful to human progress”.³⁹ It is directed at the so-called social pathologies and disorders, but its concern is humanity as a whole. This notion illustrates a project,

³⁶ Here the topic of anthropotechnics was also closely linked to the concept of psychotechnics, cf. LIGGIERI, K. Von der “Menschen-zucht”...

³⁷ Cf.: БЛОНСКИЙ, П. Педагогика. Москва: Работник просвещения, 1924, p. 11.

³⁸ See: GOFFETTE, J. Anthropotechnie: cheminement d’un terme, concepts différents..., p. 109.

³⁹ DE GOLDFIEM, J. Anthropotechnie. De la Science de l’Homme à l’Art de faire des Hommes. Auber, Paris: 1948, p. 13.

a form of *social engineering* (in a biopolitical sense), as its techniques have to “create a healthy ‘terrain’ from which a personality can emerge”⁴⁰ – a position that already implies the individual should incorporate or eradicate certain traits and characteristics in order to become a personality, a (valued, “normal”) part of the society.

A second trace of institutionalisation can be found in France in the mid-1950s. That is the Centre for Anthropotechnical Studies, under which Charles Laville published the book *Introduction à l’anthropotechnie* (1956).⁴¹ In contrast to de Goldfiem, who coined the term as a neologism, Laville, an engineer by training, presented it as an age-old practice that has now adopted a modern science-based orientation. His interpretation of anthropotechnics indicates the further turn-back from the pre-war eugenics’ doctrine, as it deems the understanding that the human being has to be rationally improved to “better adapt him to specific needs”⁴² (like labour) as rather inhumane, exploitative, and as *dirigisme*. In turn, Laville defines anthropotechnics as interested in the analysis of the dynamics in man’s “somatic and psychic variations”, which should be utilized to “improve his fate”. According to Goffette, he focuses on a “man-society symbiosis”, where the improvement of man should be harmonious and voluntary – a result of “inner discipline” – and beneficial for both sides. The author draws a distinction between zootechnics and anthropotechnics, noting that while zootechnics is employed solely for human benefit, anthropotechnics must regulate the relationship between individuals and society. In this way, the focus shifts from the population as the object of such techniques to the individual as the subject. Anthropotechnics thus serve as “a scientific (biological and social) project aimed at the optimal development of the individual and humanity as a whole, striving to push human form and society toward an asymptotic perfection. It is more a question of a project for human harmony, bodily and cultural, than of human breeding based on criteria of correspondence to the perfect type of the species”.⁴³

The neuralgic tension between (scientifically based) biological optimization and moral consciousness surrounding this topic is further illustrated by Jean Rostand, French biologist and philosopher, whose article *The Future of*

⁴⁰ Op. cit., p. 14.

⁴¹ GOFFETTE, J. Anthropotechnie: cheminement d’un terme, concepts différents..., p. 111.

⁴² Op. cit.

⁴³ Op. cit., pp. 113–114.

Biology discusses the role of technical and medical advancements in the scope of their social reception. He debates that: “the question is one not of knowing and being able, but of desiring and daring... Encouraged by our successes in zootechnics and phytotechnics, are we to go forward courageously to anthropotechnics? Are we prepared to submit ourselves to those same techniques that are astonishingly successful when applied to our livestock and our poultry? There lies the whole problem. It is a *purely moral problem* – one that it is not for scientists alone to resolve. (...) *From now on, man knows that he can work on man*. He knows the secret of how to improve himself in flesh as well as in spirit. (...) At present, he prefers to renounce this progress that lies within his reach, rather than achieve it by means that revolt him. But will he renounce it tomorrow, will he renounce it for ever?”⁴⁴

Rostand puts these questions under the well-established frame of longevity and extended health.⁴⁵ Nevertheless, he juxtaposes the notions of knowledge, moral, and distrust, as he gives examples with now established interventions (like vaccinations) that were subject of public resistance, but became normalized along with their benefits, implying a possible similar outcome for the ideas above. Hence, he stresses on the role of biologists, geneticists, etc., not only as scientists, but also as ones who should “familiarize the public with the facts”.

The critical debate, surrounding the anthropotechnics continues in the following years in lower intensity, but engaging even more points of view. The discussions reflected the new technical achievements and discoveries in the relevant fields, the changing landscape of the public health policies, particularly in sight of the historical legacy of the previous decades. They also raised new philosophical concerns, especially around issues such as personal freedom and patient autonomy. In this context, the interconnectedness between medicine and anthropotechnics remained a factor.

An example of that is the Franz Böckle’s lecture *Humane Medicine or Anthropotechnology*, published in 1971. As moral theologian, he put into the foreground the incongruity between technological and human progress, commenting not on the means, but the goals of the former. He specifically raises the

⁴⁴ ROSTAND, J. The Future of Biology. – Impact of Science on Society, II, 1951, no. 3–4, p. 88. Originally published in French in *La biologie et l’avenir humain*. Paris: Albin Michel, 1950. The circulation of the text shows its transnational significance.

⁴⁵ “It [biology] aims not only at overcoming morbid deficiencies, at normalizing the abnormal, but at improving the normal (...) Since centenarians exist, why should it not be made possible for all human beings to live for a hundred years?”, Op. cit.

question of who would (be) identify(d) as an “anthropotechnician,”⁴⁶, particularly in reference to those involved in direct patient care and clinical practice. The latter relates to the definition of the patient-clinician relationship and its ethical dimensions, as the biomedicalization of patient care during that period increasingly objectified the patient and “isolated” the related phenomena from one another. His most explicit concern was directed towards the medical experiments involving human subjects, and their applied results in the therapeutic process, stressing that the former should take into account aspects such as consent, voluntary participation, individual decision-making, etc. Böckle concludes that humane medicine (which should treat patients as subjects having physical integrity) and anthropotechnics (representing the seemingly limitless possibilities made realistic by science and technologies) must not be understood as two alternatives, but as two aspects, which should balance and even tame each other.

The latest period discussed by Goffette dates from around the early 2000’s, and it corresponds with the already-mentioned current debates surrounding the concept of human enhancement. The author sees this as possible revival of the term, emphasizing on the coexistence of two paradigms – one of optimization (with a stress on health as leading category) that suggest a “definitive state”, and one of transformation that opens a horizon of different choices, and which would be the realm of anthropotechnics.

Ergonomics, Occupational Safety and the Anthropotechnics in the Second Half of the 20th Century

Nevertheless, as detected also by Goffette, after the 1950’s the term gained yet another use, related to different contemporary fields of operation. In Germany for example, these were astrophysics and aeronautics, where the research group Anthropotechnology and Flight Measurement Techniques was established in the 1960’s. In this context, the term became more aligned with the fields of engineering and mechanics, reflecting alternative etymological links. While in the first case, the human being is the object of a set of techniques aimed at generalized refinement, in the second the focus is on the relationship between humans and technical objects or systems. This version of anthropo-

⁴⁶ BÖCKLE, F. Humanmedizin oder Anthropotechnik. – Langenbecks Arch Chiv 329, 1971, S. 20.

technics was more explicitly centred on adaptivity, effectivity and rationalization in various fields of human activities and occupation.⁴⁷

Similarly, in the USA, *anthropotechnics* became associated with the subject of aerospace, being a matter of “man-machine systems optimization” in aircraft control, and assessing the human factor in engineering. Often coupled with the term “human engineering”, this iteration puts into the foreground another form of optimisation – not of the human as such, but of the human as *machine operator*, concerning *performance, reliability, and economy*:

“(…) human engineering (anthropotechnics) strives to adapt machines to men. This involves interdisciplinary cooperation between vehicle design engineers, control systems engineers, information theorists, psychologists, and physiologists. The central research problem is seen to be the steering and controlling of dynamic systems by man (...). The anthropotechnician thus becomes a specialist, acquiring a broad range of knowledge of numerous disciplines.”⁴⁸ In this case the human’s body, mental abilities and dispositions became the object of another type of interest, as they had to be not only precisely studied, but also put into standardized metric criteria, and applied to man’s (labour) functional realities.⁴⁹

Like in its previous and upcoming uses, here anthropotechnics denotes contemporary fields and practices that were still in the making. In that case, it is one of the alternative titles of the discipline that would be most popularly known as ergonomics, being the *science of labour*. In that context anthropotechnics engages with the human-machine interface, referring to the applied processes of design and engineering of machines, technologies and systems in use of humans, regarding optimum performance, efficiency and reliability.

⁴⁷ Liggieri traces sources that came closer to this understanding. In Willy Strzelewicz’s work *Industrialization and Democratization of Modern Society* (1958), the German sociologist and educator discussed the matters of ‘Psychotechnics’, ‘Physiotechnics’, ‘Sociotechnics’ and even ‘Administrative techniques’ as sets of intertwined tools, methods, and strategies that operated at different levels for the organization and optimization of functionality, particularly in relation to industrial and work environments. Cf.: LIGGIERI, K. Von der “Menschen-zucht”..., S. 255–257. In this context the anthropotechnicians were rather public administrators, engineers and ergonomists, than medical practitioners.

⁴⁸ BERNOTAT, R., GARTNER, K.-P. *Displays and controls*; Proceedings of the Advanced Study Institute, Berchtesgaden, West Germany, March 15–26, 1971, cited from: NASA. *Aerospace Medicine and Biology. A Continuing Bibliography with Indexes* (Supplement 109). National Aeronautics and Space Administration. Washington, D.C.: 1972, p. 501.

⁴⁹ As we saw, this aspect was already present in the 1926’s Great Soviet Encyclopaedia entry.

This included taking into account the human's physical and psychic properties and their production environment. Ergonomics is concerned with "fitting" machines, operational objects and products, along with the organization of workspaces, including factors such as utility, convenience and even aesthetics. This makes ergonomics (respectively anthropotechnics) both a scientific and applied field, based again on an interdisciplinary approach.⁵⁰ According to Konov, this led to the implementation of differing headings – "anthropotechnics" in the German speaking states, "psychotechnics" in France and in Germany, "ergology" in USSR, "humans factor research" in USA, etc. This topic was not new, as the idea for "maximum efficiency with minimal health hazards"⁵¹ under the guidance of scientifically based organization of labour was prominent also in the 1920's, but the modern discipline gained a significant traction in the 1950's and 1960's.⁵² As a result, in 1959 the International Ergonomics Association was established, which led to a significant homogenisation of the discipline.⁵³ This interest was multifaceted, as it reflected the processes of industrialisation and technological advancement, the Cold-war race, and the overall transformation of the forms and the conditions of human labour – from mainly physical and manual with high motor activity, to a more technically mediated automated and attention-based types of occupation.

This presented new concerns and complex challenges regarding workers' safety, health, and wellbeing that needed a multifaceted approach, inviting specialists in the field of engineering, medicine, physiology, psychology, hygiene, economy, etc. During the same period, some of the first works discussing the standardization of the human-machine system, which included anthropometric data, were published. Henry Dreyfuss' *The Measure of Man* (1966) for instance, presents detailed illustrations and diagrams of the human body's pro-

⁵⁰ Cf.: KONOVA, C. Beginning and Periods in the Development of Ergonomics. – Proceedings of University of Ruse, vol. 58, book 1.1, 2019, pp. 99–118.

⁵¹ Op. cit., p. 101

⁵² Although the term exists from the 19th century, the worldwide institutionalization (including establishment of institutions, organization of events, and publications of special literature) began in the 20's. During the period of the Second World War, stress was placed on the optimization of the military sphere. Nevertheless, this experience was later transferred for civic usage.

⁵³ There are still nuances. According to Konov, while in Europe ergonomics were more focused on the human's physiological properties, in correspondence with their surroundings, in USA the notion of "human factors" has a more explicate connection to the behaviour sciences, see: Op. cit., p. 113.

portions while engaged in various activities such as standing, sitting behind a desk, operating a control board, driving, cycling, crouching, and more. These depictions are shown from different angles, with specific attention to age and gender variations. Along with these, schematics for basic types of equipment were added – chairs, decks, control boards, wheels, pedals and knobs, etc., together with a 360-degree view of human’s “environmental tolerance zones”. The field of ergonomics continued to develop also in the Eastern bloc, along with industrialization, padded by the requirements of the planned economy. The very notion of anthropotechnics was in use also in USSR. However, its presence was ambivalent. It was usually referred as a *foreign term* (used in GDR for example). In the *Economic Encyclopedia of Political Economy* (1972) it is noted that in the capitalist countries such disciplines are “contradictory”, as they were used for ideological purposes and for capitalist rationalization of production that further exploits the working class, eclipsing the authentic humanization of labour, i.e. the socialistic one. Still, the term was circulating during the 1960’s and 1970’s, as its explicit focus gradually shifted from the means of reproduction to those of production.

An example for that is also Bulgaria where in 1967 an Anthropotechnics section was created in the Scientific and Technical Union of Mechanical Engineering, whose chairman was Eng. Viktor Konstantinov. In 1970 a National Council on Ergonomics was organized, while a shared ambition was an ergonomics coordination centre to be established between the members of the Council for Mutual Economic Assistance.⁵⁴ As a result of their work, several international conferences were organized and a draft of an anthropotechnics terminological dictionary was prepared in 1968. Although it was not commercially available⁵⁵, the dictionary under the editorship of Konstantinov circulated among the specialists in the field, and was referenced up until the 1980’s. Its traces could be found, for instance, in the *Technical Aesthetics Journal*, where

⁵⁴ For detailed account on the initial ergonomics’ institutionalization in Bulgaria see: МАРИНОВ, Ю., ШАПКАРЕВ, П., ГИДИКОВ, А., et al. Състояние и перспективи за развитието на ергономията у нас. – Списание на Българската академия на науките, 1970, no. 4. For a visual glimpse of one of the Bulgarian ergonomic institutes see: ЦДА, ф. 720, оп. 5, а.е. 87-II, л. 166.

⁵⁵ Today a cycloprinted copy is kept in the Bulgarian National Library “St. St. Cyril and Methodius”.

it was both referred to as an alternative discipline title (the Anthropotechnics in GDR), and in scope for standardization of ergonomics terminology.⁵⁶

* * *

In the following pages I will touch on the early stages of institutionalization of ergonomics in Bulgaria in order to illustrate not only its conceptual background, but also some of its actual developments.

Similarly to the USSR, in Bulgaria the dominant notion for this scientific domain was that of ergonomics. Its aim was defined as “the optimal coordination of people’s relationships with the work environment (especially with technical means) in order to achieve maximum technical and economic efficiency in compliance with given social requirements based on the use of the achievements of psychology, physiology, anthropology, nutrition science, hygiene, biology, economics, management theory and other scientific disciplines”.⁵⁷ This understanding reflects quite literally the international scientific trends of that period – it combines the organizational, economic, and humane aspects of the issue. The insertion of the line “social requirements” denotes also the subjective levelling norms at play (i.e. the interplay between physical durability, man’s “biopotentials to control machines”, and socially acceptable work loan and working conditions, etc.).

Key figures here are the (machine) operator, the human-worker, the production team. In this context, ergonomics served a multifunctional role, addressing not only the efficiency of the overall production process but also aiming to minimize potential harms. It dealt with the design and the construction of the technical means of labour and the organization and the securing of the work environment and its possible health hazards (accidents, work overload or immobilization, air and noise pollution, lack of proper light). At the same time, ergonomics related to the personnel selection criteria, taking into account the workers’ abilities such as adaptability, training, data and sensory perception, etc., while also assessing their temperament, and intervening with their daily routine – guiding the regime of active and passive rest, the rational nutrition and diet, etc. As Man was described as the main labour force, and the care for him/her had practical and ideological implementations, this was especially rel-

⁵⁶ ТРЕНДАФИЛОВ, А. Проблемы стандартизации эргономической терминологии. – Техническая эстетика, 1981, 2(206), pp. 5–7.

⁵⁷ МАРИНОВ, Ю., ШАПКАРЕВ, П., ГИДИКОВ, А., et al. Състояние и перспективи..., pp. 20–21.

evant for the so-called ‘occupational safety and hygiene’. The latter served for “protecting workers from overfatigue, premature ageing, and the occurrence of various pathological injuries in general; rationalization of technological processes from a labour-hygienic point of view, as well as physical, chemical, biological, and other factors of the work environment and their effects on the health and work capacity of workers; the state of health of the workers, the general and occupational morbidity and their relationship with the specific conditions of labour; the negative, positive and optimal factors of labour processes and the production environment to create the most favourable working conditions; strengthening the health of workers, maximally extending the creative period and increasing labour productivity”.⁵⁸

The notion undoubtedly had a clear economic aspect, as the implementation of ergonomic interventions in the production process was expected to, on one hand, accelerate production through better utilization of working time, extended maximum productivity, fewer technical errors, and even a reduction in operational staff, and, on the other – to ensure modernized, high-quality products competitive on the international market.⁵⁹ Last, but not least, ergonomics was seen also as means to a better social and humane environment, as it was inscribed in the discourse of the human being as a harmoniously developed personality.

While the concept was quite clear and ambitious, the “coordination between science and practice” was in need of improvement. In the early 1970’s Marinov, Shapkarev, Gidikov, et al. noted the spontaneous and parcelled character of the Bulgarian ergonomics, suggesting ways of its future organization and centralization, a reflection of which, among other, was the establishment of the already mentioned National Council on Ergonomics. Despite the expanding network of ergonomic units in the country during the proceeding decade, the implementation of their work was seen as insufficient on many levels. Firstly, as it was codependent on the results of other disciplines, like that of occupational safety and hygiene, when in 1979 still “about 56.25% of workplaces in the country do not meet the sanitary and hygienic standards”.⁶⁰ Secondly, the field suffered greatly from the shortage of trained specialists, whose number was even decreasing in comparison to the first half of the 1970’s, as many

⁵⁸ Op. cit., p. 24–25.

⁵⁹ See: ЦДА, ф. 1Б, оп. 55, а.е. 745.

⁶⁰ Op. cit., p. 12.

laboratories were opened and shortly after – closed. Thirdly, ergonomics practically lacked essential material base and symbolic capital, because the units were usually supplemental to other institutions, and the weak centralization led to internal turmoil.⁶¹ As a result, the situation was described as “serious scientific and practical backlog, which is unacceptable at the current stage”.⁶²

Closing Remarks

One can note that, even when occupying a seemingly different operational sphere – namely ergonomics – anthropotechnics shares fundamental thematic commonalities with the concepts discussed above, though in a reframed manner. As we have seen, one of its key concerns is optimization and refinement, primarily aimed at the production process but also extending to the level of a common good, even to an ideological category. It focuses on the individual’s health and longevity, with an emphasis on their utility during the active period of life. It addresses evaluation and selection processes, though within a targeted scope. Nevertheless, it claims scientifically legitimized proficiency in organizing an otherwise heterogeneous segment of the population, influencing their everyday existence. Like eugenics, anthropotechnics regarded the human body as a primary object – its properties and secrets to be catalogued, deciphered, and put to “proper use”. However, its key slogan was optimization through standardization (including the environment), rather than immediate (genetic) modification. These shifts in definition and usage do not appear sudden, as some of the later aims are implied in the earlier concepts.⁶³

Using the history of a concept as an entry point, the text aimed at elaborating on the permeation of several interlinked discourses (scientific, philosophical, utopian) in fields like medicine, politics, economics and population management. It can be assumed that the semantic trajectory of the term is multifaceted, in respect of not only to its imbued connotations, but also regarding its analytical properties. While it can be a subject of investigation, today it also clearly serves as an operational analytical category. This approach puts into the foreground the social-cultural complexities that are embedded in the notion, instead of offering a strict periodisation or “categorisation” of its definitions.

⁶¹ The National Centre for Industrial Aesthetics, for instance, was assessed as in practice nonrational. Cf.: ЦДА, ф. 1Б, оп. 55, а.е. 490.

⁶² ЦДА, ф. 1Б, оп. 55, а.е. 745, л. 15.

⁶³ It is interesting to note that while the Russian-Soviet discourses offer clearer signs of continuity, the term itself loses its ideological legitimacy.

Rather, the scope of this brief historical overview was to illuminate some of the contextual nuances, transformations, and overlays of this relatively niche yet compelling notion in its idiosyncrasy, rather than offering a comprehensive historical reconstruction. At the same time, it sought to illustrate and analyse how this notion is intertwined with dynamic ideas such as achieving model forms of humanity and the concept of Man.

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